

AI Chatbots in E-Commerce: Enhancing Customer Engagement, Satisfaction and Loyalty

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ABSTRACT

The rapid advancement of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has led to the widespread adoption of chatbots in customer service, particularly in e-commerce. As part of digital marketing strategies, chatbots serve as an automated yet interactive tool to enhance customer satisfaction and foster long-term customer loyalty. This study aims to analyze the combined impact of response time, information quality, perceived usefulness (PU), and perceived ease of use (PEOU) on customer satisfaction and loyalty in the e-commerce sector. Although research on chatbot effectiveness continues to grow, most previous studies have examined these factors separately. However, no study has explored how these four variables work together not only to improve customer service efficiency but also to build long-term customer loyalty and strengthen the digital relationship between customers and brands. By employing a quantitative approach with an explanatory research design, this study surveyed 400 respondents with experience using chatbots as customer service in e-commerce companies. Structural Equation Modeling SEM was utilized to analyze the relationships between chatbot service attributes, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty. The findings reveal that all four chatbot service attributes significantly enhance customer satisfaction, strengthening customer loyalty. These results highlight the importance of integrating chatbot effectiveness into customer relationship management CRM and digital engagement strategies. By contributing to the development of CRM concepts in AI-driven customer service, this study provides insights for businesses seeking to optimize chatbot technology to enhance customer experience and build long-term relationships, as well as an addition to the literature for further research.

KEYWORDS: Chatbot, Customer service, E-Commerce, Customer satisfaction, Customer loyalty

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1. INTRODUCTION

The emergence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a transformative technology has reshaped the digital economy, particularly in customer service and marketing. AI-based chatbots have become a strategic business tool, enabling automated yet interactive customer engagement. Initially applied in industries such as education, workforce training, and technical support, chatbots are now widely used in e-commerce as part of broader digital marketing and CRM strategies (Smutny & Schreiberova, 2020). Companies are increasingly adopting AI chatbots for customer service due to the high demand for real-time interaction. Their popularity stems from users' comfort in communicating with AI in natural, human-like language (Morsi, 2023). Chatbots also automatically and implicitly learn user profiles through conversation history and generate customized responses (Ma et al., 2021). Chatbots

provide round-the-clock customer service without incurring high operational costs compared to traditional customer service models (Gkinko & Elbanna, 2023). Beyond customer service, chatbots are now central to e-commerce strategies, assisting users in navigating products, providing recommendations, and facilitating transactions directly through conversational interfaces. This integration allows e-commerce platforms to enhance customer experience by offering personalized shopping assistance and improving conversion rates (Klein & Martinez, 2023).

E-commerce is the largest Gross Merchandise Value (GMV)-contributing sector in Indonesia, accounting for approximately US\$65 billion of Indonesia's total US\$90 billion digital economy by 2024, based on the e-economy SEA 2024 report compiled by Google, Temasek, and Brain & Company. E-commerce continues to grow and innovate by offering various features to enhance

customer experience and engagement (Christa, 2024). According to SimilarWeb, Indonesia's top five e-commerce sites include Shopee, Tokopedia, Lazada, Blibli, and Bukalapak (Edot, 2024).

E-commerce companies expect chatbots used for customer service to provide accurate and timely responses. Response time is an essential element in delivering efficient customer service. In the digital age, customers expect instant and reliable responses to their inquiries. Research shows that customers experience greater satisfaction when they receive fast responses, confirming the importance of chatbot efficiency in digital customer service strategies (Gnewuch et al., 2022). However, response time alone does not guarantee the credibility and reliability of chatbot-assisted interactions. The quality of information also plays a crucial role. Users value chatbot services that provide precise and accurate information, which in turn enhances their overall satisfaction (Ma et al., 2021). The quality of the information supplied significantly influences users' trust in chatbots (Ryu & Ko, 2020). Nevertheless, chatbot responses are often superficial, too general, inaccurate, and repetitive (Zhang et al., 2024). When faced with complex or non-standard queries, chatbots usually fail to provide adequate solutions, trapping users in a cycle of unhelpful responses and ultimately serving only as an intermediary before real assistance is provided (Ozuem et al., 2024).

As AI-based chatbots in e-commerce continue to develop, customer expectations also evolve. PU and PEOU are key determinants in adopting new technologies, including chatbots for customer service (Wilson et al., 2021). PU reflects the extent to which users perceive the chatbot as beneficial, while PEOU determines how easily they can navigate and interact with the chatbot system. Businesses anticipate that AI-based chatbots will improve customer service efficiency while ensuring a seamless and user-friendly experience. A highly useful and easy-to-use chatbot encourages repeated usage, enhances satisfaction, and strengthens the digital relationship between consumers and brands through frequent and meaningful interactions (Awal & Haque, 2025).

Although research on chatbot effectiveness continues to grow, most previous studies have examined Response Time, Information Quality, PU, and PEOU separately in relation to customer satisfaction. However, no study has investigated how these four variables work together not only to enhance customer service efficiency but also to build long-term customer loyalty and strengthen the digital relationship between customers and brands as part of digital marketing strategies. Given the increasing reliance on chatbots in e-commerce, understanding the combined impact of these variables is crucial to developing chatbot services that are more effective in

enhancing customer satisfaction while fostering brand loyalty. Based on this background, this study aims to address the following research questions:

- I. How does chatbot response time affect customer satisfaction in e-commerce?
- II. How does chatbot information quality influence customer satisfaction?
- III. How does PU impact customer satisfaction?
- IV. How does PEOU influence customer satisfaction?
- V. Does customer satisfaction mediate the relationship between AI chatbots and customer loyalty?

This study explores the role of chatbots in enhancing customer engagement and brand loyalty in e-commerce. By analyzing the impact of response time, information quality, PU, and PEOU on customer satisfaction and loyalty, this study provides insights for businesses seeking to optimize digital marketing strategies, strengthen CRM efforts, and improve customer retention in a technology-driven market.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 AI Chatbot in Customer Service

Customer service is a professional commitment to providing the best possible experience by meeting customer needs through high-quality, timely, and efficient service (Al Ali, 2021). In e-commerce, live chat has become a widely used customer support tool, enabling customers to receive real-time information or solutions to technical issues. This service is crucial in building trust, enhancing satisfaction, encouraging repeat purchases, and spreading information (Adam et al., 2021). However, efficiency and effectiveness alone do not guarantee a great user experience. Companies now aim to provide customer service that is engaging, enjoyable, and even capable of exceeding customer expectations (Haugeland et al., 2022).

As an AI-driven solution, chatbots facilitate interactions through text or voice using Natural Language Processing (NLP) (Smutny & Schreiberova, 2020; Essel et al., 2022). They offer 24/7 service, improving customer engagement and operational efficiency (Gkinko & Elbanna, 2023). Chatbots generate relevant responses by processing user input in natural language while handling multiple users simultaneously. Chatbots often use first-person pronouns such as "I" or address users by name to make conversations feel more human-like, fostering a sense of connection and trust (Adam et al., 2021). However, many chatbots still fail to meet user expectations. Since humans naturally respond to social cues in communication, chatbot design should incorporate social factors to enhance interaction (Chaves & Gerosa, 2021). Unfortunately, many users prefer email over chatbots because they tend to provide repetitive and generic responses (Ozuem et al., 2024).

Moreover, chatbots struggle with complex or nuanced questions, often merely repeating FAQ content without offering meaningful solutions (Zhang et al., 2024).

Chatbot interactions often feel rigid and lack empathy, making them unsuitable for sensitive situations. While customers expect personalized engagement, chatbots frequently act as intermediaries before escalating issues to human agents (Ozuem et al., 2024). Additionally, they struggle to interpret user intent, especially with ambiguous input, unlike human agents who can clarify misunderstandings through conversation (Izadi & Forouzanfar, 2024). Although chatbots provide efficiency, they lack emotional intelligence, limiting their effectiveness in handling interactions that require empathy (Jenneboer et al., 2022). Their limited adaptability further reduces social presence, making interactions feel less meaningful (Haugeland et al., 2022). Therefore, while AI chatbots have enhanced digital customer service, their effectiveness ultimately depends on their ability to deliver relevant, personalized, and engaging responses.

2.2 Computer-Mediated Communication (CMC) Theory

CMC theory refers to human communication used or supported by computer technology (Carr, 2020). CMC represents the interaction among individuals enhanced through computer technology (Thurlow et al., 2004). The analysis of CMC encompasses six distinct levels : (1) devices that enable interaction, (2) social applications, (3) branded applications, (4) application-specific features, (5) interaction, and (6) messages (Meier & Reinecke, 2021). CMC allows individuals to stay connected despite physical absence, creating opportunities to build and maintain broad social networks. Compared to face-to-face communication, CMC has structural differences that affect social interactions, such as limited nonverbal expressions like eye contact and gestures, while increasing self-awareness through self-view features. Although CMC can be effective in various contexts, face-to-face interactions tend to create more positive first impressions and a more natural social experience (Rollings et al., 2024). As a purchasing service application, e-commerce enables transactions without direct interaction with sellers through chatbots (Klein & Martinez, 2023). Chatbots provide automated, instant, and personalized communication that mimics human agents to fulfill customer requests. However, the effectiveness of personalization remains debated, as chatbots are often perceived as incapable of delivering high-quality communication due to their limitations in adapting interactions to customer needs, preferences, and emotions (Blömker & Albrecht, 2025).

2.3 Response Time

Response time refers to how long it takes to reply to a message (Jenneboer et al., 2022). Fast issue resolution

is crucial for service recovery, helping businesses retain customers and attract new ones (Ahmed et al., 2020). In mobile applications, response time is especially critical because longer wait times lead to poor user experiences, while faster responses attract more users (Liu & Li, 2022). Chatbots help reduce wait times and enhance customer satisfaction by delivering high-quality interactions that resemble human conversations (Ruan & Mezei, 2022). However, users with prior chatbot experience may find delays frustrating as they expect instant responses (Gnewuch et al., 2022).

Chatbot response time acts as a social signal, shaping user expectations. To ensure timely and relevant information, businesses must optimize chatbot performance (Jenneboer et al., 2022). Using natural language processing, chatbots enable smooth and interactive conversations, improving engagement between users and machines (Sanny et al., 2020). Their continuous availability enhances satisfaction by making customers feel heard and valued (Rane, 2023). Reducing wait times in online interactions minimizes dissatisfaction, as perceived responsiveness directly impacts customer experience (Rane, 2023). However, speed alone does not guarantee satisfaction. Users expect fast and accurate responses, and prioritizing speed over quality can lead to frustration (Ma et al., 2021). Companies that optimize chatbot performance gain a competitive edge, improve service quality, and increase long-term customer loyalty (Ahmed et al., 2020). Additionally, excessively fast responses can make chatbots feel robotic. Introducing context-aware delays can create more natural and engaging interactions, improving overall user satisfaction (Gnewuch et al., 2022).

H1: Response time has a positive influence on customer satisfaction

2.4 Information Quality

The quality of information is assessed through individual user evaluations of various features that meet their needs and objectives (Jiang et al., 2021). It plays a crucial role in customer satisfaction and trust in chatbots (Geebren et al., 2021). If a chatbot provides low-quality information, users may perceive it as unreliable and ineffective. Accuracy and reliability are essential in building trust, making it critical for companies to ensure chatbots deliver precise and up-to-date responses (Ryu & Ko, 2020). Outdated or incorrect information can frustrate users and reduce satisfaction (Ashfaq et al., 2020). To prevent this, regular data updates are essential, ensuring chatbots provide accurate, timely, and relevant information (Izadi & Forouzanfar, 2024). AI-driven data synchronization helps detect and correct outdated or misleading content in real time, further enhancing user trust and satisfaction (Patma et al., 2021).

Chatbots handle incomplete or misleading information using NLP, machine learning, sentiment analysis, and deep learning. NLP allows chatbots to analyze language context, detect misinformation patterns, and identify biases in user queries. Sentiment and network analysis help mitigate misinformation by recognizing recurring false narratives. By integrating these technologies, chatbots can dynamically refine responses, ensuring users receive accurate and well-validated information (Saeidnia et al., 2025). However, chatbots still struggle with spelling errors, nuanced queries, and variations in user intent, highlighting the need for continuous improvements (Zhang et al., 2024).

H2: Information quality has a positive influence on customer satisfaction

2.5 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

TAM is a framework that elucidates how users perceive the utilization of technology. TAM is a widely recognized framework for identifying factors that influence technology adoption (Tahar et al., 2020). According to TAM, PU and PEOU are two main criteria influencing or predicting a person's behavior or intention to adopt a particular technology (Wilson et al., 2021). In this context, the use of chatbots as a customer service tool that can assist customers 24/7 does not automatically lead to chatbots being accepted by society (Gkinko & Elbanna, 2023). To achieve chatbot service acceptance, technological innovation in chatbot development is crucial to shaping perspectives on chatbot characteristics and their application contexts. Characteristics such as personalization for each individual based on an analysis of their communication style could be an interesting topic to explore (Murtaza et al., 2024).

PU refers to the belief that adopting assistive technology improves performance (Tahar et al., 2020). The impact of PU on work completion time, effort, cost reduction, and overall usability are key metrics (Luo et al., 2024). When customers feel that new technology offers no added value or improvement over existing products, they may hesitate to adopt it. This highlights the importance of perceived benefits for business success, especially for companies reliant on technological advancements (Wilson et al., 2021). People typically choose technologies based on their belief in the technology's ability to enhance performance. In education, for example, users' perceptions of technology's value shape their attitudes toward its use, either positively or negatively (Alfadda & Mahdi, 2021). In e-commerce, customers' views on the adequacy of product information influence purchasing decisions. Online shoppers cannot physically inspect products, so they expect accurate, relevant, and complete details from platforms. PU is also crucial in shaping post-use expectations, significantly impacting consumer

satisfaction (Akdin et al., 2022). Technology must fulfill consumers' needs and enhance enjoyment, leading to satisfaction and continued use (Yan et al., 2021). Users are satisfied when they perceive technology as beneficial, and this study defines PU as the expectation of such benefits. If customers feel that chatbots do not offer advantages or better performance compared to traditional channels, they are likely to reject them (Chaouali et al., 2024). Additionally, users accustomed to using chatbots tend to expect quick responses, while new users may tolerate slight delays. This difference in response expectations can also influence the perception of PU, as experienced users place more value on fast response times than new users, who may not yet have strong performance expectations (Gnewuch et al., 2022).

PEOU refers to how user-friendly an information system is and how little effort it requires (Schiopu et al., 2021). PEOU reflects an individual's belief that a system is easy to navigate and does not require significant effort (Dhagarra et al., 2020). Ease of use is a key factor in technology acceptance, as users' skills and comfort with technology vary across different demographics (Dhagarra et al., 2020). When users perceive a technology as easy to use, they are more likely to accept and feel satisfied with it (Uzir et al., 2021). PEOU also reflects the belief that digital tools enhance performance and streamline online communication, making interactions more efficient and seamless (Islam et al., 2023). If a chatbot interface is overly complex, with unclear navigation or too many steps, users may become frustrated and abandon the interaction. In contrast, a well-designed chatbot with intuitive features, clear conversation flows, and consistent responses enhances the user experience and builds trust (Uzir et al., 2021). Chatbots that are easy to access and navigate are more likely to be accepted as customer service tools, fostering engagement and positive perceptions (Yo et al., 2021). On the other hand, a lack of user-friendly features can discourage interaction and reduce trust, as users prefer technologies that require minimal effort to learn and operate (Wilson et al., 2021).

Companies must design chatbots based on the tasks they will perform to align with user needs (Zhang et al., 2024). Chatbot functionalities may lead to dissatisfaction and hinder adoption if they do not meet user expectations. A chatbot's benefits may diminish if users find the system too complicated and require high cognitive effort, ultimately harming the user experience and reducing adoption rates (M et al., 2024).

H3: PU has a positive influence on customer satisfaction

H4: PEOU has a positive influence on customer satisfaction

2.6 Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction measures how well a company's services align with customer expectations by delivering high-quality service and consistently meeting or exceeding consumer needs (Zygiaris et al., 2022). It reflects customers' perceptions, evaluations, and psychological reactions to their experiences with a product or service. Since satisfaction is subjective, only those who engage with the product can assess their level of contentment (Majeed et al., 2022). In customer service, satisfaction is a key metric for evaluating chatbot effectiveness (Chen et al., 2022). AI chatbots are crucial in enhancing customer satisfaction, essential for service success (Ruan & Mezei, 2022). Their impact depends on delivering accurate and contextually relevant responses. Industries like e-commerce, healthcare, and banking have shown that chatbots integrated with data-driven feedback and human intervention improve accuracy and responsiveness, leading to higher satisfaction (Izadi & Forouzanfar, 2024). However, chatbots still face limitations, such as inaccurate responses and generic interactions, which can cause frustration (Morsi, 2023). Users are particularly disappointed when human-like chatbots fail, as they expect warmth and empathy in their interactions (Zhang et al., 2024).

2.7 Customer Loyalty

Customer loyalty reflects a commitment to products, services, brands, and organizations (Magatef et al., 2023). Companies can strengthen loyalty by implementing effective loyalty programs that enhance relationships between service providers and customers (Utz et al., 2023). Loyalty is demonstrated through repeat usage, brand preference, and recommendations (Molinillo et al., 2022). Without loyalty, businesses must constantly acquire new customers to replace those who switch to competitors offering better deals (Kotler et al., 2022). Customer satisfaction is crucial in strategic marketing,

with research emphasizing its factors and effects. Satisfied customers are likelier loyal (Eklof et al., 2020). Long-term relationships are key to fostering loyalty, and service providers strive to improve it by ensuring chatbot satisfaction (Islam et al., 2023).

Customer satisfaction is essential in shaping customer loyalty behavior, reflected in their increased engagement with the company (Ali et al., 2021). The key to building loyalty is maintaining long-term relationships with customers. Service providers aim to enhance loyalty by ensuring chatbot (Raza et al., 2020). Retaining customers longer and ahead of competitors, especially in the same industry, will benefit the company (Wilson et al., 2021). However, failure in chatbot service recovery can increase the likelihood of customers rejecting their use. Dissatisfaction with chatbot performance in handling service issues may negatively impact customer loyalty toward chatbots in e-commerce (Ozuem et al., 2024). A bad experience with a chatbot can make customers reluctant to use it again, including with other brands that offer similar services (Zhang et al., 2024). Chatbots have limitations in dealing with complex issues, they are often just the first step without really saving time, and when they don't understand the problem, users are redirected repeatedly without getting help (Ozuem et al., 2024).

H5: Customer satisfaction has a positive influence on customer loyalty

Figure 1 illustrates the research framework used in this study. As shown in the diagram, response time, information quality, PU, and PEOU are the independent variables that influence customer satisfaction. Furthermore, customer satisfaction serves as a mediating variable that affects customer loyalty. Each hypothesis (H1 to H5) represents the assumed relationships among these variables, forming the foundation for the study's empirical investigation.

Figure 1: Research Framework

3. METHODOLOGY

This research methodology outlines respondent characteristics, sampling techniques, and data collection procedures while ensuring transparency, credibility, and scientific rigor. The study employs a questionnaire-based survey to examine chatbot use in e-commerce within West Java, Indonesia. The questionnaire consists of 50 questions covering screening, demographic information, and research variables, structured according to predetermined indicators. Before full implementation, a pilot survey with 40 respondents tested the questionnaire's validity and reliability. The study adopts a cross-sectional design to capture customer perceptions within a specific period. Responses are collected using a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree," allowing researchers to quantify agreement levels and generate data for further analysis of each research construct.

3.1 Respondents

In this study, respondents were selected using purposive sampling based on specific criteria determined through screening questions in the questionnaire. Eligible respondents had used a chatbot as a customer service tool, resided in West Java, and interacted with a chatbot at least once in the past month. Only those who met all three criteria could proceed with the main questionnaire. A total of 400 respondents participated, with 67.75% female and 32.25% male, mostly aged 18-25 and residing in West Java. **Table 1** shows the demographic characteristics of respondents, including gender, age, e-commerce platform used, and frequency of chatbot usage. Most respondents used the Shopee e-commerce platform, and the majority interacted with a customer service chatbot 1-2 times in the past month as such, this selection process ensured that only individuals with relevant experience towards chatbot usage participated in the study, thus increasing the validity of the data collected.

3.2 Data Collection

This study adopts an explanatory research design within the positivist paradigm, focusing on empirical testing and predictive analysis. A quantitative approach was employed, using a structured questionnaire with a Likert scale as the primary data collection tool. A pilot survey was conducted with 40 respondents before the main data collection to ensure validity and reliability. The study utilizes a non-probability purposive sampling technique, selecting 400 respondents based on Slovin's formula. The target population comprises e-commerce users in West Java Province, with a 5% margin of error to ensure representativeness. The questionnaire was administered online through a web-based survey platform and distributed to respondents who met predefined selection criteria.

3.3 Analysis Technique

This study utilizes Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with the Partial Least Squares (PLS-SEM) approach, conducted using SmartPLS 4.0. PLS-SEM was selected due to its ability to analyze complex models with multiple structural relationships while accommodating both reflective and formative measurement models. Additionally, this method is efficient for small sample sizes, does not impose strict assumptions on data distribution, and can effectively handle non-normal data, making it well-suited for this research (Hair et al., 2017). Data supporting this study are openly available from figshare.com at 10.6084/m9.figshare.28832330.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Measurement Reliability

Measurement analysis ensured validity and reliability using Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability for internal consistency. Convergent validity was assessed through AVE and outer loadings, while discriminant validity was evaluated using the HTMT method.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Category	Classification	N	%
Gender	Man	129	32.25
	Woman	271	67.75
Age	18-25 years old	317	79.25
	26-35 years old	72	18
	36-45 years old	11	2.75
E-Commerce	Shopee	275	68.75
	Tokopedia	98	24.5
	Bibli	9	2.25
	Bukalapak	3	0.75
	Lazada	15	3.75
Frequency of chatbot usage in a month	1-2 times	221	55.25
	3-5 times	146	36.5
	6-10 times	33	8.25

The results in **Table 2** indicate that the reliability of the research instrument was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability, both of which exceeded the recommended threshold of 0.7, confirming the instrument's reliability. The minimum values obtained for Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability were 0.784 and 0.785, respectively, demonstrating that the measurement model satisfies established reliability standards (Hair et al., 2017). To ensure validity, the study evaluated both convergent and discriminant validity. All constructs met the criteria, with Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values exceeding 0.5 and outer loadings above 0.7, confirming the instrument's validity, as shown in **Table 2**. As presented in **Table 3**, discriminant validity was assessed using the HTMT method, with all construct values falling below the 0.9 threshold, indicating that the constructs are distinct and valid (Garson, 2016). **Figure**

2 presents the structural model illustrating the tested relationships between variables in this study.

4.2 Structural Model Evaluation

4.2.1 Path Coefficients

Path Coefficient analysis measures the impact of AI chatbot services on customer satisfaction and loyalty. Hypothesis testing requires a T-Statistic above 1.96 and a P-Value below 0.05 (Hair et al., 2017). The results from **Table 4** show that response time, information quality, PU, and PEOU significantly influence customer satisfaction, with higher values leading to increased satisfaction. Additionally, customer satisfaction positively affects loyalty, as indicated by a T-Statistic above 1.96 and a P-Value below 0.05, meaning higher satisfaction leads to greater loyalty.

Table 2: Measurement Model Evaluation

Variable	Loading Factor	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE	
Response Time	RT1	0.731	0.803	0.807	0.559
	RT2	0.740			
	RT3	0.800			
	RT4	0.726			
	RT5	0.740			
Information Quality	IQ1	0.731	0.839	0.841	0.553
	IQ2	0.737			
	IQ3	0.736			
	IQ4	0.744			
	IQ5	0.746			
	IQ6	0.766			
PU	PU1	0.799	0.785	0.790	0.700
	PU2	0.868			
	PU3	0.840			
PEOU	PEOU1	0.726	0.784	0.785	0.537
	PEOU2	0.747			
	PEOU3	0.701			
	PEOU4	0.751			
	PEOU5	0.737			
Customer Satisfaction	CS1	0.770	0.840	0.841	0.557
	CS2	0.719			
	CS3	0.728			
	CS4	0.758			
	CS5	0.762			
	CS6	0.738			
Customer Loyalty	CL1	0.763	0.866	0.878	0.598
	CL2	0.760			
	CL3	0.827			
	CL4	0.811			
	CL5	0.705			
	CL6	0.770			

Table 3: HTMT

	CL	CS	IQ	PEOU	PU	RT
Customer Loyalty						
Customer Satisfaction	0.829					
Information Quality	0.714	0.891				
PEOU	0.566	0.803	0.688			
PU	0.679	0.844	0.805	0.691		
Response Time	0.649	0.756	0.695	0.805	0.636	

Figure 2: Structural Model

Table 4: Structural Model

	VIF Inner	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics	P values
Customer Satisfaction -> Customer Loyalty	1.000	0.027	26.997	0.000
Information Quality -> Customer Satisfaction	2.109	0.052	7.536	0.000
PEOU -> Customer Satisfaction	1.947	0.051	4.143	0.000
PU -> Customer Satisfaction	1.923	0.047	5.149	0.000
Response Time -> Customer Satisfaction	1.937	0.046	3.086	0.002

4.2.2 VIF

The analysis of the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) Inner indicates that all VIF values range between 1.000 and 2.109, remaining below the acceptable threshold of 5 (Hair et al., 2017). The results presented in **Table 4** suggest that multicollinearity is not a concern in the tested structural model. Therefore, the relationships among the independent variables do not exhibit excessive correlation, ensuring that the model estimates remain valid and reliable.

4.2.3 R²

The R-square (R²) values indicate the model's explanatory power. In this study, Customer Satisfaction has an R² of 0.689, meaning 68.9% of its variance is explained by the independent variables, reflecting a moderate to strong predictive ability (Hair et al., 2017). Customer Loyalty has an R² of 0.517, showing that 51.7% of its variance is accounted for, indicating a moderate predictive power (Hair et al., 2017). According to Hair et al. (2017), R² values ranging from 0.50 to 0.75 indicate a moderate to substantial level of explanation. The adjusted R² values (0.686 for Customer Satisfaction and 0.516 for Customer Loyalty) remain close to their respective R² values,

suggesting the model's stability in explaining these constructs. These findings indicate that while the model effectively explains Customer Satisfaction, Customer Loyalty may be influenced by other external factors.

4.2.4 Model FIT

The model fit assessment was carried out using the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) and the Goodness of Fit (GoF) index. The results show an SRMR value of 0.065, which falls below the 0.08 threshold, indicating a well-fitting model (Hu & Bentler, 1999). Additionally, the GoF index is 0.593, exceeding the 0.36 benchmark. This indicates that the model has strong predictive power in capturing and explaining the relationships among variables.

4.3 Discussion

Chatbots in customer service play a crucial role in enhancing customer engagement and satisfaction in e-commerce. This study examines the impact of response time, information quality, PU, and PEOU on customer satisfaction and how satisfaction influences customer loyalty. The results indicate that all four variables significantly affect customer satisfaction,

which in turn helps strengthen customer loyalty. Chatbots have the characteristic of having a fast response that customers need. Customers have high expectations of the efficiency of the services offered, especially regarding response speed. This finding aligns with previous research showing that response time significantly affects customer satisfaction (Sanny et al., 2020; Liu & Li, 2022; Ruan & Mezei, 2022; Rane, 2023). Customers feel more confident and satisfied when companies respond proactively to their questions and complaints (Ahmed et al., 2020). Chatbots address customer concerns in real time, reducing the risk of losing customers to competitors due to poor service (Jenneboer et al., 2022). In competitive e-commerce, companies must optimize chatbot response time to meet customer expectations. However, the extent to which response time affects customer satisfaction may vary depending on contextual factors, such as technological proficiency. Users who are already accustomed to using chatbots tend to expect a quick response, whereas new users are more tolerant of slight delays in response (Gnewuch et al., 2022).

In addition to response time, information quality is key to customer satisfaction. Customers rely on chatbots to provide accurate and relevant information for handling their queries and complaints. The results of this study align with previous research showing that companies failing to deliver quality services see a decline in customer satisfaction (Ashfaq et al., 2020). Other studies also confirm that information quality directly influences customer satisfaction (Pour et al., 2020; Kim et al., 2021; Patma et al., 2021). Therefore, companies must ensure their chatbot systems are regularly updated to provide high-quality responses and enhance the customer experience. However, providing quality information alone is insufficient to guarantee satisfaction. As Izadi and Forouzanfar, (2024) note, chatbots must also recognize diverse emotional responses and conversational styles to offer more relevant and personalized responses. This would make interactions more natural, engaging, and user-friendly. Businesses should consider integrating sentiment analysis and human-like conversational capabilities into chatbots to improve service quality.

This research shows that PU significantly impacts customer satisfaction. Customers feel more satisfied when chatbots provide valuable solutions, reinforcing their perception of chatbots as useful service tools (Yan et al., 2021). Previous studies also emphasize that PU is a key factor in shaping satisfaction (Akdim et al., 2022; Wilson et al., 2021; Yo et al., 2021). As chatbot services aim to resolve customer issues and enhance user experiences, companies must continually refine these services to ensure real benefits for users. The study also reveals that PEOU plays a crucial role in customer satisfaction. A user-friendly and intuitive chatbot interface boosts engagement, making customers more

comfortable with chatbot-based support. This aligns with previous findings that highlight the importance of PEOU in improving customer satisfaction (Uzir et al., 2021; Wilson et al., 2021; Yo et al., 2021). Innovations in customer service that are easy to use and facilitate smooth online communication are essential (Islam et al., 2023). However, Ajina et al. (2023) found that PU and PEOU don't always significantly affect satisfaction, suggesting that the impact of these variables may vary depending on other contextual factors influencing customer perceptions of chatbot services.

The relationship between customer satisfaction and loyalty has been extensively studied. This research confirms that customer satisfaction directly impacts loyalty. Satisfied customers are likelier to continue using chatbot (W. Ali et al., 2021; Raza et al., 2020; Wilson et al., 2021). Satisfied customers tend to develop a strong relationship with the company (Eklof et al., 2020). Many studies in the service sector show that customer satisfaction significantly increases customer loyalty (Islam et al., 2021). However, other research suggests that satisfaction alone doesn't guarantee loyalty, particularly in the competitive e-commerce market, where customers may switch to competitors offering better promotions (Kotler et al., 2022). This indicates that businesses should not only enhance chatbot effectiveness but also strategically incorporate chatbot services into loyalty programs. For example, chatbots can deliver personalized promotions, like birthday rewards or exclusive discounts, in real time, boosting customer engagement and retention (Nishio & Hoshino, 2024).

In addition, some confounding factors may affect the relationships analyzed in this study. One is brand reputation, which can affect customers' perceptions of chatbot services. Established e-commerce brands tend to get higher levels of customer satisfaction, regardless of the chatbot's performance (Açıkğöz et al., 2024). Similarly, prior chatbot experience could shape customer expectations, where frequent chatbot users may be more critical than first-time users (Gnewuch et al., 2022). Future research should explore these moderating effects to provide a more comprehensive understanding of chatbot adoption in customer service.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study examines the impact of response time, information quality, PU, and PEOU on customer satisfaction and loyalty toward chatbots in e-commerce customer service. The findings indicate that enhancing these factors significantly improves customer satisfaction, strengthening customer loyalty. This highlights the importance of optimizing chatbot capabilities for customer retention and long-term engagement in e-commerce. Additionally, this study reinforces

existing theories on chatbot adoption, emphasizing the role of usability and perceived benefits in shaping user behavior. Compared to previous research, these findings expand the discussion by showing that chatbot efficiency not only enhances the customer experience but also deepens digital relationships between consumers and brands. As chatbots advance, their role in customer service will evolve from a simple response tool to a key driver of brand loyalty and digital engagement strategies in e-commerce.

The practical implication of this research is that Indonesian e-commerce companies should enhance their marketing strategies to build stronger relationships with customers. Optimizing chatbot response time, information quality, PU, and PEOU can significantly improve customer satisfaction, which, in turn fosters loyalty. However, businesses must prioritize not only speed but also accuracy and personalization. AI-driven personalization enables chatbots to adapt to individual customer needs, enhancing the overall user experience. Additionally, companies should implement feedback mechanisms to continuously refine chatbot design, ensuring it remains aligned with evolving customer expectations. To maximize chatbot effectiveness, businesses should consider three key strategies: investing in chatbot personalization to enhance PU, improving response time without compromising accuracy, and continuously updating chatbot features based on user feedback. By adopting these strategies, Indonesian e-commerce companies can unlock the full potential of chatbot services and deliver a seamless, customer-centric experience.

The academic implications of this study in Indonesia provide deeper insights into chatbot effectiveness by integrating key factors influencing customer loyalty. It also expands the literature on response time, information quality, PU, PEOU, customer satisfaction, and loyalty, offering a broader perspective on chatbot adoption. This research opens opportunities for a more comprehensive analysis of factors shaping customer loyalty, particularly in technology-driven interactions. However, it has certain limitations. The reliance on self-reported survey data may lead to response bias, as perceptions do not always align with actual behavior. Additionally, cultural differences in chatbot adoption warrant further investigation to determine whether perceptions of usefulness and ease of use vary across different demographics within Indonesia. Future studies should explore the moderating role of brand reputation and user experience in strengthening the chatbot-loyalty relationship. Moreover, research should assess the long-term impact of chatbot interactions on customer trust, including comparisons between voice-based and text-based chatbots to determine their influence on loyalty and engagement.

Going forward, AI and NLP advancements will further enhance chatbot capabilities, enabling more intuitive and context-aware interactions. GPT-based chatbots will better understand complex queries and respond with greater situational awareness, optimizing the customer experience. Improvements in sentiment analysis and emotional intelligence will allow chatbots to recognize and respond to customer emotions more personally, enhancing engagement and satisfaction. These innovations not only boost service efficiency but also reshape digital engagement strategies. As AI-powered chatbots become more widespread in e-commerce, businesses must continuously refine their technology to strengthen chatbot-human interactions, build trust, and drive long-term brand loyalty through ongoing innovation.

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